

Student Satisfaction **towards** College Canteen Services in Chitwan and Nawalparasi District, Nepal

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Abstract

Every student experiences hunger and seeks to satisfy it with clean, well-balanced foods. College canteens have been established to meet this need, serving as essential gathering places where students can enjoy delicious and nutritious meals. This study utilised a non-experimental descriptive correlational research design to investigate the correlation between student satisfaction and the quality of canteen services in the Chitwan and Nawalparasi districts. A total of 103 candidates responded to the questionnaires, which were distributed to them on a completely random basis. The data from these 103 samples were analysed using statistical tools to measure canteen service quality across parameters such as assurance, empathy, reliability, responsiveness, and tangibility. Based on elements like facilities, features, ambiance, cleanliness, and cost, the satisfaction of students was evaluated. Multiple metrics were employed to enable a multi-dimensional assessment. The study involved stringent data filtering and the use of relevant analytical tools to enhance the reliability and precision of insights into the relationship between service quality and student satisfaction. The findings showed that students perceived the level of service at the canteen as moderately satisfactory, with overall student satisfaction at a moderate level. A notable correlation was identified between the level of canteen services and student satisfaction, highlighting specific aspects such as tangibility and empathy that influence this association. Hence, the study recommends that college canteen managers prioritise improving service quality by directing their attention to the two variables identified as significant indicators of student satisfaction.

Keyword: *cleanness, correlation, quality of services, regression, students' satisfaction.*